

Secure and Reliable Digital Wallets: A Threat Model for Secure Storage in eIDAS 2.0

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Abstract. The revised eIDAS regulation (eIDAS 2.0) advocates a shift back to user control over digital credentials, introducing the European Digital Identity Wallet. This shift aims to enhance privacy by allowing citizens to disclose personal data in a controlled manner selectively. As the keys to which the credentials are bound must be stored securely, a secure storage mechanism is essential—one that is not only secure but also accessible through the available technology stack and compliant with eIDAS 2.0.

In support of the European Digital Identity Wallet, the EU Commission published an Architecture and Reference Framework together with a set of Implementing Acts to ensure interoperable solutions. However, the current versions only identify a high-level set of requirements and do not provide insights on satisfying them through actionable implementations. Secure storage is a crucial aspect that remains inadequately addressed, highlighting the need for comprehensive security and privacy guidelines to ensure a robust solution. To address this gap, we provide a threat model explicitly designed for the secure storage component of the wallet. This allows for identifying potential threats and a set of effective controls to secure the implementations and serves as a practical tool to assist architects in making informed decisions when selecting an implementation that best meets their system’s security and privacy requirements. In addition, it reinforces essential assurance activities, such as certification, testing, and attestation required by the eIDAS 2.0 to maintain a trusted state for secure storage.

Keywords: Digital Identity Wallet · Secure Storage · Threat Model.

1 Introduction

In the modern digital landscape, digital identity wallets have become critical for securely managing and storing user credentials, playing a central role in electronic identification and trust services. Within the European Union (EU), the

European Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW) initiative, introduced under the new electronic Identification, Authentication, and Trust Services (eIDAS 2.0) regulation, represents a significant advancement toward secure and user-centric digital identities [17]. To ensure interoperability and security, the European Commission has proposed the EUDIW Architecture and Reference Framework (ARF), which outlines technical guidelines and best practices for EU member states to implement secure and privacy-preserving wallet solutions [18].

A crucial component of the EUDIW security architecture is the Wallet Secure Cryptographic Device (WSCD), responsible for secure key management, authentication processes, and cryptographic operations. Given its role in handling these operations, the security of WSCD is essential to guarantee the confidentiality and integrity of user data both within the EUDIW, and during its interaction with the EUDIW on the user’s device. Here, the concepts of trust, trustworthiness, assurance, and attestation, in turn, are crucial to maintaining the security and reliability of users’ personal and sensitive data, such as cryptographic key material protected by WSCD [29, 45].

In this context, “trust” refers to users’ confidence in the EUDIW implementation and, more specifically, their certainty that the WSCD operates securely and as intended; it is subjective and influenced by past experiences, manufacturer reputation, and transparency in security practices. Trustworthiness is the objective quality of the WSCD, reflecting its ability to consistently perform secure operations, resist threats, and comply with standards such as FIPS 140-3 [35] or Common Criteria [14], which is also mandated by eIDAS 2.0 regulation [3, 17]. Assurance encompasses the processes that demonstrate and validate this trustworthiness, such as testing and certification. Attestation adds a real-time verification layer, offering cryptographic evidence that the WSCD remains in a trusted state. These concepts are interlinked: trust arises from perceived trustworthiness, which is reinforced through assurance mechanisms and maintained over time through attestation [7, 43]. As assurance mechanisms play an enhanced role in sustaining trust, they must go beyond static evaluations. While certification and rigorous testing provide assurance for WSCD during the production phase, real-time verification during its operation is necessary to maintain trust. This can be achieved through attestation, typically via signed statements or cryptographic certificates, proving the WSCD remains untampered and compliant with security policies.

To make such efforts effective, it is essential to develop a comprehensive threat model. Threat modeling plays a critical role in ensuring trustworthiness, as it enables the proactive identification and mitigation of attack vectors before they can be exploited. This is particularly vital for EUDIW solutions, which manage personal data such as identification data. A structured threat model informs the design of protective measures and security controls that reduce exposure to these risks.

For example, the WSCD must be hardened against threats that could compromise users’ private keys, thereby undermining the trust placed in the EUDIW. Threat modeling allows for such risks to be systematically identified and

addressed through targeted controls. It is also interlinked with assurance activities: for certification, a robust threat model ensures that regulatory requirements are met while accounting for real-world attack scenarios. In testing, it directs efforts—such as penetration testing and vulnerability scanning—toward the most critical attack surfaces. In attestation, it defines the parameters that must be continuously verified to confirm the WSCD remains in a trusted state.

Despite its centrality, threat modeling is not yet adequately addressed in existing regulatory frameworks and technical guidelines, leaving a critical gap. While the Implementing Act (IA) [16] defines high-level security requirements and the ARF provides technical guidance, neither includes a detailed and systematic threat modeling methodology tailored to WSCD implementations. This gap creates uncertainty about specific threats, vulnerabilities, and asset risks, potentially exposing WSCD architectures to sophisticated threats such as side-channel exploits, unauthorized key extraction, or software tampering [6, 37, 48].

To address these limitations, this paper proposes a structured threat modeling approach tailored specifically to WSCD deployments within the EUDIW framework. Building on our prior research [46], which examined general EUDIW threats, we extend our analysis by explicitly focusing on secure storage threats, vulnerabilities, and necessary controls relevant to various WSCD architectures. Our contributions are:

- Systematically identifying, categorizing, and contextualizing threats applicable to WSCD using established frameworks such as STRIDE [32] and LINDDUN [30].
- Mapping identified threats and vulnerabilities to effective security controls in alignment with ARF and eIDAS 2.0 regulatory requirements.
- Providing a reference threat model to assist Wallet Providers and EU regulators in developing secure and privacy-preserving WSCD solutions.

By establishing threat modeling as a key component of assurance—integrating testing, certification, and attestation—we aim to significantly enhance the security and reliability of EUDIW implementations, ultimately contributing to a robust digital identity infrastructure across the EU.

Paper Structure. Section 2 presents the method we follow to perform the WSCD threat modeling in the context of EUDIW that provides a brief explanation of the WSCD components, and our threat characterization. In Section 3, we report our findings and share lessons learned. Section 4 contrasts our approach with related works. We summarize the main results and provide insights for future work in Section 5.

2 WSCD Threat Modeling

This section describes the method used for WSCD threat modeling, building upon our previous work in [46], which involves the following steps:

Fig. 1: Overview of WSCD in the EUDIW ecosystem and its internal components. The Interfaces, Assets, and Services are detailed in Table 2.

Context Establishment is an initial step to provide a complete understanding of the WSCD component. It helps to pinpoint the critical assets and understand how the WSCD component interacts with EUDIW.

Threat Characterization focuses on identifying potential threats and attack scenarios relevant to the WSCD. It categorizes threats by their sources, categories, and the assets they target. Additionally, it outlines vulnerabilities, along with the security controls needed to mitigate the identified threats.

2.1 Context Establishment

The EUDIW is an application developed by an entity called “Wallet Provider” in the ARF [18]. The EUDIW, when installed on a User device, is a user-controlled application that allows them to store and manage their digital credentials such as their personal identification data, or mobile driving licenses.

According to the ARF [18], the EUDIW can be implemented as a single mobile application. This application integrates multiple components to support its core functions, primarily the secure issuance and presentation of credentials. A key component in the EUDIW ecosystem, as shown in Figure 1 is the Wallet Secure Cryptographic Device (WSCD), which is hardware-backed storage and manages keys and implements cryptographic suites and mechanisms essential for credential issuance and presentation. The WSCD itself includes many components at the hardware level, including data or key storage, and many services which you can find in Figure 1. We further list all of them in Table 2 and describe them in Section 2.2. Additionally, the EUDIW includes a Wallet Secure Cryptographic Application (WSCA), which leverages the WSCD’s capabilities via two interfaces: the Secure Cryptographic Interface (SCI) between the EUDIW and WSCA, and the WSCA and WSCD Interface (WWI) between the WSCA and

WSCD. While the former is specifically designed to manage cryptographic assets and execute cryptographic operations using the WSCD, the latter is specifically designed to enable communication between the WSCA and the WSCD. The security of the WSCD component is of great importance to avoid the release of credentials to an EUDIW that cannot securely store private keys as highlighted in Annex 2 of ARF (WUA_08 requirement) [18]. The security and capabilities of the WSCD can be attested by the Wallet Provider by acquiring a key attestation from the WSCD component of the EUDIW. This attestation is known as Wallet Unit Attestation (WUA) as defined by the ARF [18], which is issued by the Wallet Provider and ensures that the keys used for key binding of credentials reside in a trusted WSCD.

As illustrated in Figure 1 and Table 1, WSCDs can be configured in diverse architectures. Local hardware-based solutions include on-device modules—such as processor-native environments (e.g., Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) or integrated security co-processors) and embedded Secure Elements (SEs), such as Embedded Subscriber Identity Modules (eSIMs)—as well as external, user-held SEs (e.g., Java-based smart cards). Remote solutions, such as Hardware Security Modules, provide centralized key management and high security from data centers. Hybrid setups combine on-device and remote approaches for balanced security, scalability, and flexibility. Building on this architectural diversity, Table 1 provides a detailed overview of these WSCD types by comparing them across key aspects: form factor, advantages, and limitations. Specifically, for local, processor-native TEEs, the table highlights their embedded form factor, flexible updates, and security profile compared to the Rich Operating System (Rich OS)- the main, general-purpose OS like Android or iOS - but with a different

Table 1: Comparison of WSCD Types

Feature	Secure Element (SE)	Trusted Execution Environment (TEE)	Hardware Security Module (HSM)
Deployment Type	Local (Embedded and External)	Local Native	Remote
Form Factor	Embedded SE: Integrated Logic chip on device motherboard (e.g., eSIM, Android StrongBox). External SE: Portable, off-card-based (e.g., smart cards, secure USB tokens).	integrated within main CPU architecture (e.g., Android Keystore). Dedicated security coprocessor (e.g., Apple Secure Enclave).	Standalone appliances or server modules (e.g., rack-mounted, in data centers).
Advantages	High security, widely used in IoT and mobile devices. External SEs: Portable, easy to replace or upgrade.	Flexible, integrates with existing hardware, supports secure software updates, offers strong performance.	High security and performance, suitable for enterprise and critical infrastructure.
Limitations	Embedded SEs: Less flexible, difficult to upgrade. External SEs: Limited processing power, may not integrate seamlessly with other hardware.	Requires specific hardware support, implementation requires complexity.	High cost, large form factor, implementation requires specialized hardware.

security profile compared to dedicated SEs and HSMS. In contrast, embedded SEs typically integrate seamlessly at the hardware level, although upgrading them can be challenging, while external SEs are portable but often have limited processing power. Alternatively, remote solutions such as HSMS in secure data centers provide high-level security, centralized cryptographic key and operational security management (monitoring, audits). However, they may introduce additional costs and complexity and generally require constant connectivity.

2.2 Threat Characterization

In the following, we present our main results concerning the list of identified assets and threats.

Assets. We categorize the assets into data, services, and interfaces that require protection as highlighted in Table 2, with illustrative examples shown in

Table 2: Asset Categorization in WSCD Threat Modeling

Category	Asset	Description
Data	User/Holder Keys (UK)	Symmetric and asymmetric keys (e.g., private keys) managed by the WSCA, essential for cryptographic operations and securing sensitive user interactions within the EUDIW.
	WSCD Authentication Data (WAD)	Credentials and authentication tokens, such as the PIN/passwords, required for secure access to the WSCD resources and services.
	Client Application Data (CAD)	Holder-specific data, such as credentials, provided by the EUDIW for cryptographic functions; requires confidentiality and integrity protection.
	WSCD Data (WD)	Core application code, such as the WSCA code, libraries, and sensitive WSCD security data, including secure keys, logs, support keys, key management information, and update code packages.
Service	Key Management Services (KMS)	Services for key generation, secure access, rotation, and secure destruction within the WSCD to maintain controlled and protected key lifecycles.
	Cryptographic Operations Services (COS)	Essential cryptographic functions such as encryption/decryption, digital signing, verification, and hashing, ensuring data confidentiality, authenticity, and integrity within the EUDIW context.
	Authentication Services (AS)	Authentication mechanisms for verifying the identity of the Holder and the authorized device accessing the WSCD.
	Access Control Services (ACS)	Authorization and monitoring services, including audit logging, to control and oversee access to the WSCD resources.
	Secure Communication Services (SCS)	Encrypted transmission using protocols like TLS/SSL to secure data in transit, with end-to-end encryption and message integrity checks.
	Data Protection Services (DPS)	Encryption and integrity protection measures for securely stored data, safeguarding against unauthorized access and tampering.
	Backup and Recovery Services (BRS)	Services for securely backing up and recovering keys and critical data to prevent data loss and ensure resilience.
	WSCD-specific Security Services (WSS)	Dedicated security mechanisms, including tamper detection, secure boot, and application isolation, to protect against physical and logical threats.
Interface	Secure Cryptographic Interface (SCI)	Interface facilitating secure data exchange between the EUDIW and the WSCA, ensuring controlled cryptographic interactions.
	WSCD and WSCA Interface (WWI)	Interface governing secure data flow between the WSCD and the WSCA, ensuring data integrity and enforcing access control.

Figure 1. For example, secure storage within the hardware boundary of WSCD contains data assets, while key management and cryptographic services enable secure cryptographic operations using them. Overall, grouped by function and importance, these assets support secure operations within the EUDIW. Data assets involve sensitive information such as cryptographic keys and authentication data. Service assets include essential cryptographic functions, such as key management and secure communication. Finally, interface assets enable secure interactions between the WSCD, WSCA, and the EUDIW.

Threats. We consider threats as any potential violations of the WSCD security or privacy, including unauthorized access, data modification. We identified a list of **23** threats, here we report a subset of **10** threats, which are summarized in Table 3 and are later discussed in a discussion section. Due to page limits, for each threat, we selectively report relevant attack techniques, vulnerabilities, and controls rather than providing a comprehensive list. Readers interested in a complete list with detailed information can refer to our companion website [4]. Table 3 includes:

- **Threat Category (TC):** The entry in the threat category categorizes each threat using two established frameworks: STRIDE [32] and LINDDUN [30]. STRIDE, developed by Microsoft, serves as a mnemonic for security threats, covering Spoofing (SP), Tampering (TA), Repudiation (RE), Information Disclosure (ID), Denial of Service (DS), and Elevation of Privileges (EP). LINDDUN focuses on privacy threats, including Linkability (LN), Identifiability (IF), Non-Repudiation (NR), Detectability (DT), Data Disclosure (DD), Unawareness/Unintervenability (UU), and Non-Compliance (NC).
- **Attack Techniques (AT):** Describes strategies that attackers use to exploit threats, which are taken from academic literature [33, 43, 48], and technical reports [19–21, 44].
- **Vulnerabilities (V):** Highlights weaknesses like weak cryptographic protection, which could be exploited by specific threats, which are taken from widely recognized standards [37, 38].
- **Affected Assets (AA):** Identifies impacted elements like Secure Communication Services (SCS) under specific threats.
- **Controls (C):** Lists measures such as Strong Authentication to counteract threats like **T1**. Data Disclosure. The identified controls are mostly taken from the technical reports [19–21, 44].
- **Affected WSCD (AW):** Reports the affected WSCD type for each threat.

Table 3: An excerpt of threats to the WSCD in the EUDIW ecosystem.

<p>T1. Data Disclosure involves compromise of Holder data, which is potentially accessed physically or remotely [21, 38]. <i>TC:</i> ID, DD <i>AT:</i> (AT1) Side-channel attack (e.g., the attacker extracts side-channel information by monitoring physical leakages like power consumption, electromagnetic emissions to infer secrets like cryptographic keys, or other sensitive data without direct access to the IC internals)</p>
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V: Weak cryptographic protection (V1), Weak access control mechanisms (V2), Insecure communication channels (V4), Poor credential management (V7)
AA: UK, WAD, CAD, WSD, SCS, DPS, SCI, WWI
C: Isolation (Physical and Logical) (C1), Side-Channel mitigation (C4), Data encryption (C7), Integrity protection (C8), Secure communication channels (C19)
AW: All

T2. Data Manipulation involves the threat actor trying to manipulate the Holder data in storage or during transfer [20, 21, 44].

TC: SP, TA, DD
AT: (AT19) Man-in-the-Middle (e.g., an attacker intercepts and alters communication between the User and the WSCD, allowing them to capture credentials and impersonate the User to gain unauthorized access and manipulate the data)
V: Weak access control mechanisms (V2), Lack of data integrity mechanisms (V5), Weak authentication mechanisms (V6), Insufficient or Inadequate code signing/verification (V10)
AA: UK, WAD, CAD, WAPD, WSD, SCS, DPS, COS, KMS, SCI, WWI
C: Integrity protection (C8), Key management (C10), Access control (C17), Secure communication channels (C19)
AW: All

T4. Physical Tamping involves the threat actor trying to modify or exploit the physical security measures to access WSCD [20, 23, 26, 36].

TC: EP, DS, TA, NC, DT
AT: (AT5) Perturbation (e.g., an attacker could attempt to introduce intentional disturbances or variations to a system's environment to induce errors or reveal sensitive information and extract confidential data)
V: Inadequate physical security (V8), Weak key management practices (V13)
AA: All WSCD assets
C: Tamper-Resistant hardware (C2), Anti-tampering (C13), Self-testing (C25), Security audits (C26)
AW: All

T6. Key Disclosure/Compromise involves unauthorized access to the plain text form of a secret key, allowing direct reading, copying, or compromising of the key by an attacker [38, 49].

TC: ID, EP, NC
AT: (AT25) Attacks to cryptographic algorithm implementations (e.g., Attacker targets the implementation of cryptographic algorithms within the WSCD, such as exploiting weaknesses in random number generators to predict cryptographic keys or breaking encryption due to implementation flaws)
V: Weak cryptographic protection (V1), Weak access control mechanisms (V2), Weak authentication mechanisms (V6), Poor credential management (V7)
AA: UK, KMS
C: Secure cryptographic implementation (C6), Data encryption (C7), Key management (C10), Zeroization of keys (C27)
AW: All

T12. WSCD Malfunction involves a WSCD fault, which is causing security properties to weaken or fail [49].

TC: TA, NC
AT: (AT2) Fault injection (e.g., an attacker intentionally introduces faults or errors into a system or device to cause malfunction and reveal sensitive information. This can be done by inducing physical perturbations during cryptographic computation or by algorithm parameter manipulation)
V: Inadequate error handling (V14)
AA: All WSCD assets
C: Monitoring and logging (C21), Self testing (C25), Security audits (C26), Error handling (C32)
AW: All

T15. Unauthorized Code Execution involves the threat actor trying to import malicious code into WSCD to disclose or modify sensitive data. Includes executing malicious applications with illegal byte-code sequences or invalid parameters [19, 23].

TC: TA, NC, ID, DD
AT: (AT24) Software/firmware modification (e.g., the attacker modifies the software/ firmware of the WSCD, introducing vulnerabilities or backdoors that can be exploited to compromise its security)
V: Improper validation of integrity check value (V11), Improper input validation (V12), Insecure card and applet management (V18), Vulnerable applet execution controls (V19)
AA: All WSCD assets

C: Secure debug (C14), Control flow integrity (C15), Secure firmware and software update (C24), Secure APIs (C28)
AW: TEE, SE

T18. Unauthorized Card Management involves the threat actor trying to perform unauthorized card management operations (e.g., by impersonating the card issuer or applet provider) to take benefit of the privileges or services granted to this actor on the card and perform fraudulent operations like loading, installing, deleting, extracting, or personalizing an applet, or updating privileges [21].

TC: TA, SP, EP, NC
AT: (AT16) Key replacement (e.g., the attacker replaces a valid card issuer key with a malicious one to gain unauthorized access or control)
V: Insecure card and applet management (V18)
AA: WAPD, WSS, WSD, KMS, ACS
C: Secure card and applet management (C22)
AW: SE

T20. Applet/ Application Impersonation involves a threat actor forging the identity of a trusted entity (e.g., an applet in an SE or a Trusted Application (TA) in a TEE) to gain unauthorized access to WSCD resources, services, or data. Examples include impersonating a TA in a TEE environment or a legitimate applet in a SE [23,36].

TC: SP, ID, EP, DD
AT: (AT16) Key replacement (e.g., the attacker replaces a TEE trusted key, or an issuer’s public key, with a malicious one to gain unauthorized access or control)
V: Insecure card and applet management (V18), Vulnerable applet execution controls (V19)
AA: WAD, AS, ACS
C: Access control (C17)
AW: TEE, SE

T21. WSCD Cloning involves the threat actor trying to copy WSCD-related data from one device to another, making the second device accept it as genuine [23].

TC: SP, ID, EP, DD
AT: (AT7) External DRAM probing (e.g., an attacker tries to retrieve the TEE code or data by probing data on an external RAM bus to analyze the TEE behavior, to find vulnerabilities in the TEE and use this vulnerability to attack the TEE)
V: Inadequate data cloning protection (V20)
AA: All WSCD assets
C: Data cloning protection (C30)
AW: TEE

T22. RAM Exploitation involves the attacker gaining access to device RAM, potentially accessing sensitive runtime data like cryptographic keys, authentication data, or other confidential information [23].

TC: ID, EP, DD, NC
AT: (AT10) Breach of memory isolation (e.g., An attacker can try to directly access and modify TEE memory contents by exploiting a flaw in hardware memory isolation)
V: Improper input validation (V12), Lack of memory protection (V22)
AA: UK, WAD, WSS
C: Secure boot (C5), Secure I/O (C11), Memory protection (C12), Security audits (C26), Secure APIs (C28)
AW: TEE

3 Discussion

In our threat modeling, we identified **23** distinct threats, **23** vulnerabilities, **32** controls, and **28** attack techniques extracted from various sources, including widely recognized standards (e.g., OWASP [38,39]), technical reports [19–21,44], and academic studies [8,33,47]. The identified threats apply to various WSCD solutions, including TEE, SE (embedded and external), and HSM. These WSCD types as mentioned in Section 2.1, and shown in Table 1 represent different categories outlined in the ARF: local native, local embedded, local external, and remote, reflecting the diversity of secure storage technologies used within the EUDIW framework.

The insights gained from our threat modeling analysis form the basis for the following lessons learned:

- Of the **23** identified threats, **16** (69.6%) apply to all WSCD types, **2** (8.7%) apply only to TEE, another **2** (8.7%) apply only to SE, and **3** (13%) apply to both TEE and SE. This classification per architecture type, highlights better the trade-offs between WSCD types as it provides per-architecture threat profiling. To elaborate, let us consider “T22. Ram Exploitation”, TEE-based solutions are vulnerable specifically to this threat, where an attacker may access sensitive runtime data due to the reliance on software-based isolation mechanisms to protect sensitive data during runtime. This reliance, coupled with the shared use of hardware resources between secure and non-secure environments, can make TEEs vulnerable to attacks that exploit weaknesses in the software stack or runtime memory management [23]. While this is not the case for other WSCD types. Similarly, SE-based solutions (e.g., smart cards or eSIMs) face additional risks, such as “T18. Unauthorized Card Management”, which necessitates extra security measures tailored to their architecture [21].
- Among our list of threats, “T4. Physical Tampering”, “T5. Faulty Update Code Package”, “T12. WSCD Malfunction”, “T13. Functionality Abuse”, “T15. Unauthorized (Ill-formed) Code Execution”, and “T21. WSCD Cloning” deserves the most attention to mitigate as if these threats are carry out, the results are the comprise of all WSCD assets. Given that, these require the highest priority for mitigation efforts.
- Information Disclosure (**13** out of **23**) and Elevation of Privilege (**12** out of **23**) are the most common security threat category identified in our analysis. Both threats involve sensitive data, whether contained in WSCD storage, transferred between WSCD and authenticated external entities using a client application (e.g., EUDIW), or transmitted between physically separate components of the WSCD. The impact of Elevation of Privilege is particularly severe, as it enables attackers to gain unauthorized access to WSCD functions and data, potentially leading to misuse or unauthorized cryptographic operations. In contrast, the impact of Information Disclosure is less immediate but can provide attackers with data that could be leveraged for more specialized attacks in subsequent stages.
- Non Compliance (**16** out of **23**) and Data Disclosure (**8** out of **23**) are our analysis’s most prevalent privacy threats. While Non-Compliance is a critical threat to avoid, as failure to adhere to regulations could expose User’s data to unauthorized access and result in hefty fines from regulatory authorities, the impact in the case of Data Disclosure can be a significant risk as the attacker can access the User’s sensitive data such as their private keys which enables attackers to decrypt User’s stored credentials.
- Integrity Protection (C8), Key Management (C10), Authentication (C16), Access Control (C17), Secure Card and Applet Management (C22), Security Audits (C26), and Secure APIs (C28) deserve additional attention in contrast to the other controls as they are mitigating multiple threats (**4** up to **10**

threats) if implemented. Rather than C22 and C26, which are SE and HSM-specific controls, the rest are applicable to all WSCD types.

- Access Control (C17), Authentication (C16), Security Audits (C26), and Key Management (C10) are among the top security and privacy controls within our analysis; however, each also involves a trade-off between robust security and ease of implementation. Access Control (C17) requires not only complex policy management (e.g., role-based or attribute-based) but also demands continuous alignment within the WSCD that can lead to various challenges within the implementation. To elaborate, let’s consider the case of local native and embedded SEs WSCD types. In the context of local native WSCD solutions, access control enforcement relies heavily on the host operating system’s authentication, authorization, and process isolation mechanisms. Vulnerabilities or misconfigurations in the OS can compromise policy enforcement. Furthermore, in the case of embedded SEs, as they often have limited memory, processing power, and bandwidth, these constraints lead to imposing limitations on how access control logic is enforced (e.g., limited policy complexity, and limited secure storage). However, in case this control is implemented properly, it effectively mitigates threats such as unauthorized access (T17), impersonation (T3), and data disclosure (T1). In the context of Authentication (C16), it is important to have a balance between security and usability. While this control can be integrated at a fundamental level by integrating well-established protocols and APIs to safeguard access to the WSCD, it may generate user inconvenience if the solution necessitates frequent or multi-step credential verification processes. Despite its relative ease, it remains effective in preventing unauthorized credential use and reducing impersonation attempts (T3). Security Audits (C26) demand specialized logging and analysis tools, raising both the expertise needed to maintain and analyze them. This continuous scrutiny ensures that Wallet Providers remain well-informed about potential vulnerabilities, ultimately contributing to a more robust security posture. Finally, Key Management (C10)—encompassing advanced cryptographic techniques and ensuring reliable key generation, distribution, and storage—poses a more demanding control to implement. However, it is highly effective in mitigating threats such as key disclosure (T6), thereby ensuring that private keys remain protected against a broad range of security threats targeting the WSCD.

Practical Considerations. Integrating WSCDs into the EUDIW framework requires a careful balance between stringent security requirements—particularly compliance with the eIDAS High assurance level as mandated by the ARF—and practical challenges like user convenience and offline functionality. Building on our earlier work [3] that highlighted these complexities, we further examine the intricate trade-offs in WSCD selection. To support Wallet Providers in making informed development decisions, we define the following set of criteria:

- **User Reachability:** Accessibility and user adoption potential of the WSCD technology.

- **Security:** WSCD compliance with the eIDAS High assurance requirement, as specified under Common Criteria (CC) vulnerability assessment AVA_VAN.5, whether nationally or at the EU level [3,14].
- **User Convenience:** Smooth, intuitive user experience and user-centric design.
- **Offline Use:** determines whether the WSCD technology meets the requirement to operate without network connectivity.
- **Backup and Restore:** WSCD support for secure backup and restore of hardware-bound keys.

Each of the WSCD solutions is analyzed in the following based on the listed criteria, with a summary provided in Table 4.

Local native. Local native WSCD solutions, such as TEEs are more widely implemented across a broader range of devices, thus satisfying the high range of user reachability. Concerning security, these solutions provide a baseline level of security (CC AVA_VAN.3), which does not meet the eIDAS High assurance requirement. Users need to set a password or biometric within the EUDIW solution to enable access to the WSCD functionalities, thereby ensuring a seamless user experience. Lastly, as the cryptographic materials and WSCA are hosted locally on the user’s device, this WSCD type can easily support offline use-cases. Moreover, the keys are bound to the device WSCD and together with the other cryptographic materials are not exportable.

Embedded SEs. These WSCD solutions, such as eSE (e.g., Strongbox in Android), or eSIM are starting to become more accessible in the markets. According to a report published by Counterpoint [13], half a billion eSIM-capable devices were shipped worldwide in 2023 and it is estimated that by 2028 most of the European population will have an eSIM-capable device [1]. From a security standpoint, many embedded SEs—such as those found on high-end phones—already hold high-assurance CC certifications (CC AVA_VAN.5), whereas eSIM implementations generally still require that evaluation to demonstrate the security guarantees needed for EUDIW use cases. Because the SE resides entirely on the user’s device, these solutions deliver seamless convenience and naturally support offline operation. However, like local TEEs, their keys are permanently bound within the SE and cannot be exported, so no backup or key-migration functionality is available.

External SEs. These WSCD solutions, typically take the form of NFC-enabled smart cards—most commonly government-issued identity (ID) cards—that act as portable WSCDs. Their adoption is hindered by the still-limited penetration of NFC-capable smartphones and the fact that mandatory issuance of ID cards only began in August 2021 [15]. The provided ID cards by member states are generally certified to CC AVA_VAN.5. Concerning user’s convenience, smart cards do not provide a user-friendly experience as it requires the user to carry and tap their card for each interaction. On the plus side, because only NFC

connectivity is needed, they fully support offline use cases. As with other local WSCD types, the cryptographic keys are permanently bound to the SE and cannot be exported, so no backup or restore functionality is available.

HSMs. Hardware Security Modules are widely adopted in the industry in different use cases for encryption, decryption, digital signature, authentication, and payments, as they must be deployed in the cloud—separate from the user’s device—reachability is not a problem, since accessing HSMs from the EUDIW is merely a matter of implementing an API call. Regarding security, HSMs can meet the eIDAS High assurance requirement when certified under CC AVA_VAN.5. User convenience is low, as interactions between the EUDIW and a remote HSM require strong user authentication that can add an additional burden on the user experience. However, HSMs do not support offline use cases as the EUDIW needs to be connected to the internet to access the remote modules. As HSMs operate in cloud environments, they routinely allow encrypted key backups and disaster recovery mechanisms as part of standard operational procedures. The backups remain protected (e.g., encrypted) and can be restored to a compatible HSM without exposing the actual private keys in the clear.

To sum up and synthesize our findings, we highlight the following key insights:

- Among local mobile solutions, embedded SEs, such as Android’s StrongBox (on CC AVA_VAN.5-certified high-end devices) or eSIMs, offer superior security through tamper-resistant hardware for cryptographic operations. However, their adoption is limited: StrongBox is primarily available on select Samsung models and a few Google Pixel devices, covering only a small percentage of the European mobile market [27,31]. This coverage could expand if Apple’s Secure Enclave achieves compliance with eIDAS High, enhancing security. For eSIMs, adoption is similarly constrained but projected to reach high penetration by 2028 [1]. Nevertheless, a significant portion of users remain reliant on less secure alternatives (e.g., TEEs)—certified only at CC AVA_VAN.3 or external/remote options—certified at AVA_VAN.5 but hindered by usability and connectivity challenges—limiting their immediate suitability.
- HSMs provide a promising level of the eIDAS High assurance requirement (CC AVA_VAN.5), satisfying ARF mandates, but their integration into the EUDIW presents substantial challenges for Wallet Providers. First, developing a robust interface to connect the EUDIW with secure back-end modules is complex. Second, additional security measures are required to safeguard front-end interactions with these HSMs. Moreover, practical concerns—such as limited offline support and the need for scalable, high-performance back-end systems—make HSM deployments costly and intricate, potentially deterring widespread adoption.
- As a transitive solution, local native TEEs (e.g., Qualcomm’s TEE [22]) offer broad reachability across mid-range and budget devices, despite providing only baseline security (CC AVA_VAN.3), which falls short of the eIDAS High assurance requirement (CC AVA_VAN.5) [16]. A phased approach leveraging TEEs initially ensures immediate accessibility and user

adoption while embedded SEs and HSMs mature in terms of market penetration, certification, and cost-effectiveness. This strategy balances usability and security, addressing current needs while preparing for robust, standardized implementations.

Table 4: Trade-off Analysis of WSCD Technologies

WSCD Type	User Reachability	Security (CC AVA_VAN.x)	User Convenience	Offline	Backup
Local Native (TEEs)	High (widespread)	Basic (CC AVA_VAN.3, not eIDAS High)	High	Yes	No
Local embedded SEs	Growing (eSIM 2028)	Cert. req., potential eIDAS High	High	Yes	No
Local external SEs	Low (NFC limits)	Certified (CC AVA_VAN.5, eIDAS High)	Low	Yes	No
Remote HSMs	High (cloud API)	Certified (CC AVA_VAN.5, eIDAS High)	Low	No	Yes (encrypted)

4 Related Works

Several studies underscore the crucial role of threat modeling methodologies when combined with secure storage technologies to enhance system security. For example, research has effectively applied STRIDE and DREAD frameworks alongside TEEs and SEs. These efforts address threats like spoofing, data disclosure, denial of service, and unauthorized access across various systems [12, 25, 34, 42], consistently demonstrating the benefits of secure storage in protecting sensitive operations and data identified through threat modeling. Complementing these high-level treatments, component-level threat analyses have shown that assumed “trusted” hardware boundaries often conceal critical vulnerabilities. For instance, Cerdeira et al. cataloged numerous implementation flaws and insecure interfaces in ARM TrustZone TEEs, enabling attackers to escape the secure world and compromise the non-secure world [11]. Brassler et al. demonstrated how code-reuse and state-rollback techniques can bypass Intel SGX enclave isolation guarantees [9]. Likewise, Park et al. showed that a single side-channel trace is sufficient to recover private keys from hardware cryptocurrency wallets [40], and Kepkowski et al. revealed how timing side-channels can defeat phishing-resistant protections in FIDO2 authenticators [28]. In the smart-card domain, Ahmed et al. found that embedding secrets in a tamper-resistant SE with HSM-backed recovery significantly mitigates threats from device theft and malware [2]. Industry protection profiles such as EN 419221-5, the ANSSI CC Protection Profile, and the GlobalPlatform Protection Profiles further enumerate attacker capabilities and prescribe hardware countermeasures [5, 10, 21]. Finally, broader STRIDE- and attack-tree-based surveys by Grüner et al. and Pöhn et al. confirm that while secure enclaves raise the cost of attack, a comprehensive component-level threat model is essential to cover all TEE, SE, and HSM variant-specific risks [24, 41].

Taken together, these system-level and component-level studies establish that formal threat modeling paired with hardware roots of trust is both necessary and effective.

Within the EUDIW framework, where the WSCD functions as secure storage, the IA [16] itself provides a foundational, high-level threat identification that acknowledges potential threats to WSCDs within the ecosystem. However, this initial assessment remains at a high level, and importantly, it does not delve into detailed threat modeling of the internal components and diverse architectural implementations of this critical secure storage.

Similarly, our previous threat modeling work [46] performed a general threat modeling of the EUDIW ecosystem. While it focused on the main entities and primary operational phases like credential issuance and presentation, it intentionally considered the WSCD as a secure storage black box, explicitly leaving its internal threat landscape out of scope.

As non of the aforementioned studies, nor the EUDIW IA offer a component-level threat model for the WSCD, this paper presents a targeted and structured threat model focused precisely on the WSCD. Our study offer a granular analysis of threats and vulnerabilities across different WSCD architectures relevant to the EUDIW ecosystem.

5 Conclusion

The introduction of EUDIW under the eIDAS 2.0 regulation represents a significant step towards giving back the users control over their data. The ARF offers a general reference architecture, and the IA provides foundational guidelines for implementing EUDIW solutions. However, their broad, high-level approach fails to adequately address critical security and privacy aspects, such as secure storage mechanisms. While certification and testing may ensure WSCD security during the production phase, real-time verification during operation is crucial. In this context, threat modeling is key to strengthening security. A clear threat model ensures that WSCD solutions meet regulatory requirements and address real-world attacks, enhancing security beyond compliance. Without it, critical threats like side-channel attacks, key extraction, or software tampering may be missed, leaving systems vulnerable. Despite its crucial role, threat modeling has not been adequately addressed in the existing ARF and IA documents, leaving a critical gap.

This research paper fills the identified gap by presenting a structured and targeted threat model specifically tailored to secure storage—also referred to as WSCD—within the EUDIW framework. Leveraging STRIDE and LINDDUN frameworks, our research identifies, contextualizes, and categorizes potential threats, mapping them to vulnerabilities, attack scenarios, and impacted assets. Furthermore, we listed a set of actionable security controls to mitigate these threats and to address the ARF requirements. The developed reference model not only serves as a practical tool for Wallet Providers, enabling the design of secure and privacy-preserving EUDIW implementations, but also guides assurance activities to reinforce certification, testing, and attestation. By addressing the

evolving threat landscape and aligning with the eIDAS 2.0 standards, this work contributes to a more robust digital identity ecosystem, ultimately improving user trust and security. As a preliminary step to conducting an accurate and effective risk assessment, knowing what potential threats exist is essential.

In future work, we plan to enhance our threat model by incorporating a control-based risk assessment methodology that systematically quantifies risks and maps them to specific security controls, ensuring alignment with best practices. In addition, by indicating the priority or mandatory implementations per each control, we aim to assist the Wallet Providers to take an informed decision by implementing the most effective measures for risk reduction. This will highlight how EUDIW risk levels evolve with different deployments of WSCD and based on the implementation of selected controls.

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